

Experimental Assessment of Neural 3D Reconstruction for Small UAV-based Applications

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Abstract—The increasing miniaturization of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) has expanded their deployment potential to indoor and hard-to-reach areas. However, this trend introduces distinct challenges, particularly in terms of flight dynamics and power consumption, which limit the UAVs’ autonomy and mission capabilities. This paper presents a novel approach to overcoming these limitations by integrating Neural 3D Reconstruction (N3DR) with small UAV systems for fine-grained 3-Dimensional (3D) digital reconstruction of small static objects. Specifically, we design, implement, and evaluate an N3DR-based pipeline that leverages advanced models, i.e., Instant-ngp, Nerfacto, and Splatfacto, to improve the quality of 3D reconstructions using images of the object captured by a fleet of small UAVs. We assess the performance of the considered models using various imagery and pointcloud metrics, comparing them against the baseline Structure from Motion (SfM) algorithm. The experimental results demonstrate that the N3DR-enhanced pipeline significantly improves reconstruction quality, making it feasible for small UAVs to support high-precision 3D mapping and anomaly detection in constrained environments. In more general terms, our results highlight the potential of N3DR in advancing the capabilities of miniaturized UAV systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) has rapidly increased and is expected to continue growing [1]. As UAVs become smaller, their potential applications can be expanded in the direction of operating in more diverse and confined environments such as indoors and hard-to-reach areas. However, this miniaturization also brings distinct challenges, particularly regarding flight dynamics and power consumption [2]. Smaller UAVs encounter issues such as reduced power density in electromagnetic motors, transmission inefficiency due to increased friction in bearings and gears, and greater viscous losses due to decreased Reynolds numbers. Furthermore, flight modes like hovering become more energy-intensive and difficult to control as UAV sizes decrease. These scaling issues fundamentally limit the autonomy of UAVs, thereby restricting their ability to carry out complex missions [2].

Beyond UAV miniaturization challenges, 3-Dimensional (3D) reconstruction and anomaly detection are key enablers for applications like infrastructure inspection and precision

manufacturing. Traditional methods struggle with small UAVs and fine-scale objects due to sensor limitations such as low-resolution cameras, limited field of view, and motion blur, resulting in incomplete reconstructions with occlusions, shadows, perspective and scale errors, etc. Systems integrating N3DR with miniaturized UAVs are currently lacking, yet they are envisioned to offer a solution to these challenges by enhancing accuracy, mitigating artifacts, and enabling high-fidelity reconstructions. Aligned with this vision, we introduce an N3DR-based pipeline for the 3D digital reconstruction of small static objects using images captured by a single or fleet of small UAVs. Advances in technology have enabled even small UAVs to capture images of static objects, generating datasets that can be processed by N3DR models to create 3D object representations. We employ a nano-UAV (i.e., Crazyflie 2.1) system for 3D reconstruction of a small object, leveraging N3DR to enhance the quality of reconstructions. Three state-of-the-art models, i.e., Instant-ngp [3], Nerfacto [4], and Splatfacto [5], are evaluated using datasets of images from both single and multi-UAV setups. A comprehensive set of imagery and pointcloud metrics is used to evaluate the resemblance between the reconstructions and a 3D-printed object. The results highlight the performance of the N3DR models and demonstrates the feasibility of using small UAVs in combination with N3DR for 3D anomaly detection.

A. Main Contributions

a) *Redefining evaluation methodologies for small-scale 3D reconstruction:* As 3D reconstructions shift toward smaller objects and scenes, traditional evaluation methodologies designed for macroscopic-scale reconstructions are starting to lose relevance. Our results reveal that metrics such as Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), Learned Perceptual Image Patch Similarity (LPIPS), and Wasserstein Distance (WD) lack the resolution to capture subtle variations in small-scale objects. This study emphasizes the need for new evaluation frameworks tailored to fine-grained geometric discrepancies. While Splatfacto provides the highest reconstruction accuracy, Nerfacto exhibits more stable performance across different objects, making it preferable for anomaly detection. These findings highlight

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the necessity of revising evaluation methodologies for N3DR applications in small-scale robotics.

b) Advancing 3D reconstruction and anomaly detection toward micro-scale: As recent advances in robotics are enabling device and system miniaturization, there is an increasing need for advanced computational techniques that operate effectively at small scales. This paper demonstrates that N3DR pipelines leveraging state-of-the-art models can enhance 3D digital reconstruction and anomaly detection using small UAVs. By system downsizing, this study contributes toward the long-term vision of wireless robotic materials, which are distributed computational structures capable of self-monitoring and adaptation [6], [7]. The evaluation of single- and dual-UAV setups, along with location-aware reconstruction, demonstrates that even resource-constrained UAVs can contribute to fine-grained anomaly detection, paving the way for future applications in ultra-miniaturized robotics.

II. RELATED WORKS

Photogrammetry is an established technique for extracting shape information from physical objects and scenes [8]. It is widely used in applications such as topographic mapping, archaeology, architecture, infrastructure maintenance, and gaming [9]. Photogrammetry involves capturing multiple images from different viewpoints and using them to calculate the 3D coordinates of an object’s surface. This method is particularly effective when combined with Structure from Motion (SfM), which does not require prior knowledge of camera positions, making it more flexible than traditional stereo imaging techniques that mimic human binocular vision [10].

SfM has been widely adopted due to its robustness and ability to handle large datasets [10]. It reconstructs 3D structures by identifying matching features across overlapping images, estimating camera positions, and triangulating points to create a sparse 3D pointcloud. This approach is advantageous as it does not necessitate precise camera positioning or prior knowledge of camera intrinsic parameters, which can instead be estimated directly from the images. However, despite its flexibility, SfM-based methods struggle with reconstructing fine-grained objects, particularly when working with low-resolution sensors or when image sequences contain occlusions, shadows, or perspective distortions.

N3DR-based techniques have emerged as a promising alternative, leveraging deep learning to improve reconstruction accuracy, mitigate artifacts, and enhance fine-scale detail extraction. N3DR synthesizes novel views of an object or scene by learning an implicit volumetric representation from a set of images [11], [12]. Although N3DR provides high-fidelity reconstructions, its computational complexity presents a challenge for near-Real Time (RT) applications, particularly in resource-constrained platforms such as miniaturized UAVs. Several state-of-the-art N3DR models have been developed, each optimizing different aspects of the reconstruction.

Instant-ngp introduces a multi-resolution hash encoding that accelerates training while maintaining reconstruction accuracy, making it particularly suitable for near-RT applications [3].

This encoding optimizes feature vectors in each iteration for improved memory efficiency, with performance influenced by feature vector size, hash table dimensions, and resolution.

Nerfacto, an advanced Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF) implementation from Nerfstudio [12], [4], refines camera poses via backpropagated loss gradients, addressing errors stemming from inaccurate camera positioning and slight motion artifacts. A piecewise sampler distributes samples efficiently, while a proposal sampler focuses on key scene areas, using a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP)-based density function with multi-resolution hash encoding. The density field determines object presence, while the Red, Green and Blue (RGB) field specifies color. After training, these fields enable NeRF visualization and scene rendering, producing a pointcloud from ray samples and generating a mesh through Poisson surface reconstruction.

Splatfacto [5], based on Gaussian Splatting (GS), employs CUDA-accelerated differentiable rasterization to optimize scene representations, significantly reducing the computational cost associated with NeRF-style reconstructions. It initializes 3D Gaussians based on sparse SfM points, projects them into 2-Dimensional (2D) space using camera parameters, and refines density using adaptive control. The dynamic texture refinement process aligns projections with input images, generating gradients that iteratively refine Gaussian shape and color. The final optimized Gaussians enable scene rendering using a Gaussian-based method.

By comparing these techniques, this study evaluates the feasibility of N3DR-driven reconstruction for small UAVs, considering key factors such as accuracy, computational efficiency, and robustness to imaging artifacts. Although traditional SfM-based methods remain relevant in some scenarios, N3DR approaches offer superior performance, particularly in cases where high-fidelity reconstructions are required despite low sensor resolution and constrained computational resources. The integration of these models with lightweight UAV-based imaging systems has the potential to significantly enhance autonomous 3D mapping, anomaly detection, and inspection capabilities in constrained environments.

III. EVALUATION METHODOLOGY

A. Evaluation Setup

We use a small-UAV-based experimentation infrastructure designed for autonomous 3D reconstruction of small static objects, as shown in Figure 1. The infrastructure employs lightweight Crazyflie 2.1 UAVs (cf., Figure 2), each weighing less than 100 grams, integrated into an open-source pipeline for near-RT 3D reconstruction.

The system leverages the Loco Positioning System (LPS) for UAV localization. The LPS consists of Ultra Wide-Band (UWB) anchors distributed across the environment and a tag attached to the UAV. After the anchors are positioned and calibrated, the system localizes the UAV with the average accuracy of less than 10 cm [13], achieved through Time Difference of Arrival (TDoA)-based multilateration.

The UAVs are equipped with cameras that capture black-and-white images from various angles, which are wirelessly

Figure 1: Hardware and software setup

Figure 2: Crazyflie 2.1

transmitted to a ground station for 3D model generation. The near-RT reconstruction capability allows dynamic adjustments to the UAVs’ flight paths based on the RT quality of the 3D model, optimizing both coverage and accuracy. Both single- and dual-UAV configurations are considered, operating in two modes: *baseline 3D reconstruction*, where only the images are used for reconstruction, and *location-aware 3D reconstruction*, where positional data from the LPS is combined with the images to improve accuracy.

B. Evaluation Methodology

The results of each experiment are the render, mesh, and pointcloud visualizations of a reconstructed object. The pointclouds are used in evaluation due to their wide utilization and availability of programmatic frameworks for the metrics’ calculation. The reference object is indicated in Figure 1, which was 3D-printed for the evaluation. The resulting 3D-printed object features the size of $54.7 \times 20.3 \times 20.9 \text{ cm}^3$, with the letters and engravings having a depth of 4 cm.

The alignment between a reconstructed pointcloud and a reference was performed as follows. Pointcloud orientation and scaling consistency were achieved by computing scaling factors from bounding box ratios and employing fast global registration and principal component analysis for orientation correction. Alignment was refined through global registration techniques based on feature matching and the iterative closest point algorithm. Post-alignment, virtual cameras were generated uniformly around the object and directed towards its center, to render images from both the reference and reconstructed pointclouds. Performance metrics were subsequently calculated directly from the pointclouds or from comparisons with the rendered images. The utilized metrics are:

- **PSNR** is the ratio between the maximum possible signal power and the noise affecting its quality, used to compare the Mean Squared Error (MSE) between images and renders.
- **Structural Similarity Index (SSIM)** indicates similarity between images and renders, with 1 being perfect similarity. This metric compares luminance, contrast, and structure differences across the image samples.
- **LPIPS** is the perceptual similarity between the images and the 3D render.

- **Hausdorff Distance (HD)** captures the overall deviation of a reconstruction as the maximum distance between the points in the reference and reconstructed pointclouds.
- **WD** calculates the minimum “work” required to transform a reconstructed pointcloud into the reference, measuring the cost of transporting points between the two.
- **Reconstruction latency** refers to the total time taken to calculate a full reconstruction from the input images for the SfM approach. The latency for the N3DR approaches will be captured as the time required for generating the final pointcloud representation, which combines the model training and pointcloud rendering.

To enable anomaly detection, we establish a quantitative comparison between the reconstructed object and a known reference. The anomaly detection process consists of computing the baseline metric on interest for a reconstructed object that does not feature an anomaly, comparing it against a reference object without anomalies. This is followed by computing the metric for a reconstructed object that contains an anomaly, using the same reference object without anomalies. Finally, we calculate the difference in the metric for a reconstructed object with and without the anomaly, which quantifies the structural difference introduced by the anomaly. This approach allows for both quantitative and spatial anomaly detection. The magnitude of the difference provides an indication of how pronounced the anomaly is, while spatial anomaly localization can be achieved by analyzing the differences between the reconstructed and reference pointclouds.

C. Image Preprocessing

The images are processed through sharpening and brightness adjustments, which were empirically optimized to improve the reconstruction quality, as shown in Figure 3. As illustrated, the edited images capture more distinct features around the object compared to the originals, leading to more robust feature detection. This is evident in the matches between consecutive frames that are more consistent in the edited images, as shown by the clustering and detection of feature points. The grouping of images, based on the UAV’s yaw and timestamp, ensures coherent surface and structure reconstruction, further enhancing the fidelity of the 3D model.

(a) 1206 features on original (b) 1513 features on processed

Figure 3: Improvements due to image preprocessing

Figure 4: Hyperparameter optimization for Nerfacto

D. Hyperparameter Tuning

In the considered N3DR models, the hyperparameters optimized include the allowed maximum iterations for both the feature matching algorithm and the localizer estimator during the SfM process. These parameters were uniformly set across all tests to ensure consistent comparisons. During feature matching, the Random Sample Consensus (RANSAC) algorithm [14] is used to filter out incorrect feature matches that do not conform to a consistent transformation. RANSAC works by randomly sampling subsets of feature matches and fitting a model to them, followed by evaluating how many other matches are consistent with the model. By adjusting the number of allowed iterations, the computational time can be reduced, but this may result in noisier reconstructions and potentially lower quality. The number of iterations for the localizer estimator and the feature matching algorithm was set empirically. An example is depicted in Figure 4 for Nerfacto, with the brown vertical line indicating the selected number of iterations. Our aim was to strike a balance between reconstruction accuracy and execution time.

There is a discrepancy between the metrics’ values presented in the hyperparameter optimization in Figure 4 and the final results. During hyperparameter tuning, the PSNR, SSIM, and LPIPS metrics are calculated based on the rendered images of the scene, directly comparing the quality of the rendered output to a reference. This image-based evaluation typically shows higher metrics due to the nature of 2D evaluation. In contrast, the final results are calculated from the pointclouds of the scene rather than the rendered images, and demonstrate lower

values (cf., Tables I and II). This is due to pointcloud-based evaluation being more stringent, focusing on the accuracy of the 3D geometry and structure, which is more sensitive to small deviations. This decision was made with the understanding that the hyperparameter tuning process focused on providing a near-RT reconstruction capability, prioritizing efficiency. While extended training would yield slightly better results, the iteration limits were tuned to deliver acceptable reconstruction quality within a constrained execution time.

IV. EVALUATION RESULTS

In Table I, we overview the 3D reconstruction performance in case the object of interest does not feature an anomaly. The performance is assessed for the three considered N3DR models and the SfM baseline along the heterogeneous set of metrics overviewed in Section III-B. When comparing the single- and dual-UAV setups, it is visible that the inclusion of the second UAV does not benefit the reconstruction performance across all metrics and approaches. This suggests that a sufficient number of images was collected in a single-UAV setup for reaching the performance limits across approaches, with the number of images as indicated in Table I. In other words, the reported performance is constrained by the inherent limitations of N3DR for the given set of low quality images. For this reason, in the remainder we focus on the single-UAV setup.

The objects generated by N3DR are collections of several small pieces which might appear hollow from certain angles. This phenomenon is observable on the results, because the AI-based solutions did not improve or yielded only marginal improvements in terms of PSNR, SSIM, and LPIPS compared to the SfM baseline. This is because the imagery metrics are derived using images rendered from the object with randomly chosen cameras. The pointcloud metrics are based on the inspection of the objects, so they are immune to this effect.

One can observe that not all metrics fluctuate significantly across the considered approaches. This is primarily the case for PSNR, LPIPS, and WD that remain at constant values of respectively 7.7 ± 0.2 , 0.05 ± 0.01 , and 0.016 ± 0.002 across approaches. We argue that the lack of sensitivity is caused by the fact that the object for reconstruction is rather small. The majority of the current literature targets the reconstruction of comparably larger objects, which intuitively feature larger reconstitution errors and, therefore, larger difference in the reconstruction when compared to the references. Due to the fact that PSNR, LPIPS, and WD lack sensitivity to reflect the differences between reconstruction quality of the assessed approaches, we consider the other metrics as more relevant and focus on them in the remainder of the paper.

The utilization of location coordinates stemming from the LPS in addition to the ones obtained through SfM (i.e., location-aware solution) does not significantly benefit the reconstruction accuracy. The reason for that can be found in the fact that the locations provisioned by the LPS coordinate system feature certain errors, with its average value in the range of 10 cm, as reported in [13]. Nonetheless, the location-aware approach enhances the reliability of pointcloud generation

TABLE I: Performance of different approaches for 3D reconstruction of an object without an anomaly

Approach	PSNR [dB]	SSIM	LPIPS	HD	WD	Latency [s]	# images taken	# images used
Single-UAV system - Baseline								
SfM	7.405	0.972±0.006	0.050±0.007	0.077	0.0285	271	233	232
Instant-ngp	7.750	0.956±0.008	0.052±0.009	0.039	0.0152	757	233	232
Nerfacto	7.565	0.960±0.007	0.042±0.007	0.027	0.0164	444	233	232
Splatfacto	7.730	0.971±0.007	0.049±0.012	0.033	0.0171	302	233	232
Single-UAV system - Location-aware solution								
Instant-ngp	7.989	0.957±0.008	0.052±0.009	0.039	0.0188	876	233	232
Nerfacto	7.710	0.963±0.006	0.040±0.008	0.025	0.0165	493	233	232
Splatfacto	7.852	0.969±0.007	0.044±0.011	0.033	0.0140	314	233	232
Dual-UAV system - Location-aware solution								
Instant-ngp	7.750	0.957±0.009	0.050±0.009	0.033	0.0156	783	466	465
Nerfacto	7.642	0.963±0.006	0.039±0.007	0.025	0.0164	475	466	465
Splatfacto	7.666	0.967±0.008	0.049±0.009	0.035	0.0152	302	466	465

TABLE II: 3D reconstruction performance for an object with anomaly and anomaly detection using HD metric

Approach	PSNR [dB]	SSIM	LPIPS	HD	WD	Latency [s]	HD_B	HD_A	ΔHD
Baseline									
SfM	7.195	0.971±0.006	0.060±0.010	0.072	0.0469	306	0.077	0.092	0.015
Instant-ngp	7.212	0.952±0.008	0.058±0.009	0.034	0.0164	754	0.039	0.073	0.034
Nerfacto	7.319	0.960±0.007	0.044±0.007	0.024	0.0141	465	0.027	0.062	0.035
Splatfacto	7.745	0.970±0.008	0.048±0.010	0.039	0.0177	302	0.033	0.070	0.037
Location-aware solution									
Instant-ngp	7.254	0.955±0.009	0.054±0.009	0.034	0.0148	837	0.039	0.076	0.037
Nerfacto	7.341	0.962±0.006	0.042±0.007	0.025	0.0152	470	0.025	0.076	0.051
Splatfacto	7.285	0.971±0.006	0.045±0.009	0.034	0.0161	310	0.033	0.074	0.041

Figure 5: 3D reconstruction capabilities for different approaches for single-UAV system

Figure 6: 3D reconstruction capabilities for different approaches for dual-UAV system

by offering an additional source for provisioning of camera locations. In other words, using SfM to obtain coordinates is only feasible if the aligned images contain enough features for accurate camera localization, whereas the location-aware approach allows the UAV location coordinates to be used as an alternative source. This can be observed in Figures 5 and 6 by comparing the baselines and location-aware methods, where it is observable that the utilization of location-awareness increases the density of the resulting pointclouds compared to the corresponding baselines. Intuitively, the advantages of context-aware approaches are anticipated to be more significant for larger target objects in reconstruction, where the image density relative to the object’s size is lower.

As depicted in Figures 5 and 6, the usage of N3DR benefits the 3D reconstruction accuracy, density, and quality. Focusing first on the metrics comparing the quality of 3D reconstruction to the input images, Splatfacto yields the best performance. Specifically, as visible in Table I, Splatfacto outperforms Nerfacto and instant-ngp in terms of the SSIM and latency metrics. In addition, it visually yields the best quality of reconstruction when compared to the alternative approaches, as observable in Figures 5 and 6. Based on this observation, we argue that Splatfacto can provide the best visual quality of reconstruction, which, for the considered small scale objects, can be captured by utilizing the SSIM and latency metrics.

Table II presents the performance derived for the reference

Figure 7: Demonstration of anomaly detection capabilities using single-UAV setup and Nerfacto

and the reconstructed object with anomaly. The aim is to assess the consistency of the metrics for different objects for reconstruction, yet with comparable physical sizes. As visible by comparing the single-UAV setup performance in Table I with the corresponding performance of different approaches for a slightly modified object in Table II, Nerfacto provides the most stable performance in relation to the object shapes. This is a desired feature for anomaly detection applications, in which different objects should be reconstructed with comparable accuracy, which is a precursor for anomaly detection.

An example spatial detection of an anomaly is depicted in Figure 7 for the Nerfacto model. The anomaly consisted of a set of boxes covering the lower part of the letters on one side of the object, as depicted in Figure 7a. The difference ΔHD between the HD distances of the object with and without the anomaly can be used for detecting the anomaly and its magnitude, as shown in the figure.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE EFFORTS

The integration of N3DR with small UAV-based systems for 3D digital reconstruction has proven to be an effective approach to addressing the limitations posed by such UAVs. The utilization of N3DR models significantly enhances the accuracy and realism of the reconstructions, even with the constraints in sensor quality. Future research can explore several areas to build upon this work to refine the technology.

One promising avenue is the incorporation of RGB cameras, which would enhance the richness and detail of the captured images compared to the currently leveraged black-and-white ones. The inclusion of color data would likely improve the quality and realism of 3D reconstructions, particularly when dealing with complex textures or surfaces. Improving the localization accuracy of small UAVs presents another opportunity. Current systems suffer from tracking inaccuracies, which can negatively affect the precision of 3D reconstructions. Future work should focus on refining localization techniques to ensure that data is captured with greater spatial accuracy.

Additionally, future assessments should evaluate the performance for larger objects to confirm its general applicability for various scales of reconstruction. A methodology that adjusts the small UAV system based on the size of the object could be developed. This would involve optimizing parameters like UAV positioning, flight patterns, and data collection rates in response to different object sizes, ensuring scalability while maintaining accuracy. There is a potential to optimize 3D

anomaly detection within these systems. The use of alternative distance metrics, such as mean instead of the currently utilized maximum distance, could lead to more precise and reliable detection. Further research could enhance the system's ability to detect subtle discrepancies in reconstructed models, thereby expanding its utility to a broader range of applications.

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